

CONDITIONS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL PERSONAL QUALITIES OF FUTURE EDUCATORS

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Annotation There are various forms and methods of developing the skills of future educators, and they can be implemented step by step. Among the many forms and methods aimed at developing competence in working with educators, the following can be distinguished: Seminar - creative classes aimed at developing creative thinking and creating innovative projects. game modeling business and role-playing games involve the modeling of a real process, during which optimal professional decisions are made based on the analysis of artificially created pedagogical situations. Collective problem solving, group discussion or brainstorming; trainings in small groups to improve professional skills, methods of self-education, scientific and practical conferences on the results of innovative activities of preschool educational institutions.

Key words: personal, professional, creative, educator, value, information, foreign, process, thinking, methodical, pedagogical, competence, foreign countries, social, personal qualities

Аннотация. Существуют различные формы и методы развития навыков будущих педагогов, и их можно реализовывать поэтапно. Среди множества форм и методов, направленных на развитие компетентности в работе с педагогами, можно выделить следующие: Семинар – творческие занятия, направленные на развитие творческого мышления и создание инновационных проектов. игровое моделирование деловые и ролевые игры предполагают моделирование реального процесса, в ходе которого принимаются оптимальные профессиональные решения на основе анализа искусственно созданных педагогических ситуаций. Коллективное решение проблем, групповое обсуждение или мозговой штурм; тренинги в малых группах по повышению профессионального мастерства, методам самообразования, научно-практические конференции по результатам инновационной деятельности дошкольных образовательных учреждений.

Ключевые слова: личностный, профессиональный, творческий, педагог, ценность, информация, зарубежный, процесс, мышление, методический, педагогический, компетентность, зарубежные страны, социальные, личностные качества.

The skill of a teacher is a high pedagogical thinking, a conscious, creative approach to the educational process, the ability to effectively apply methodical knowledge. information about 'and modern information technologies, experiences of advanced foreign countries are theoretically included in the learning process. The more quality our teachers are and the more they love their profession and educate preschool teachers, the brighter the future of our youth will be. No matter what profession a person is engaged in, if he approaches his work and training diligently and lovingly, he will perfectly master its secrets, at the same time, he will realize himself and find perfection in this field. Competency assessment should not be understood as a single level of competence, but rather a complete set of competencies manifested in various process situations during the long time spent by a person to achieve his goals of personal importance. For the teacher who interacts with preschool children every day and monitors their development, it is necessary to teach the child to engage in mental processes related to education, to activate psychomotor development with appropriate pedagogical tools, and to help the development of the child's general and musical abilities. Thus, a sufficient level of practical experience, speech, memory and perception increases the child's self-confidence. The child is capable of setting goals of various complexity, the achievement of which has a positive effect on the volitional characteristics of behavior. Also, a number of changes take place in the motivational field of preschool children: a system of interrelated motives is formed, which ensures the general direction of behavior, the ability and need for education, and the motivation for a positive attitude towards the surrounding people develop rapidly. Step by step, older preschoolers master moral assessment, begin to take into account the sequence of personal actions, feel hope for the result and the assessment of adults. One of the forms of using ICT in the development of professional personal qualities of future educators is a lesson-presentation. In order to develop the creative potential of students, the lesson can include solving creative problems, writing essays, reports, crosswords on the topic, creating and implementing projects, using interactive creative tasks. Another advantage of the Power Point program for teachers of future preschool educational organizations is the availability of various bright colors and the ease of working with animated images when creating visual materials for classes (events, competitions).

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